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Which are the most promising protein sources for meat alternatives?

Bruno Etter^{*}, Fabienne Michel, Michael Siegrist

ETH Zurich, Department of Health Science and Technology (D-HEST), Consumer Behavior, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Meat alternatives have the potential to shift people's diets into a more sustainable direction. To improve consumers' attitudes to meat alternatives and increase the likelihood of their consumption, it is important to identify the most promising protein sources from a consumer perspective. This study investigated expectations toward 17 specific protein sources applied in meat alternatives and four conventional animal-based protein sources across six rating dimensions in an online survey with 916 participants from the German-speaking part of Switzerland. Additionally, several relevant consumer characteristics, namely food neophobia, health consciousness, preference for naturalness, environmental identity, and consumers' attitudes to meat and meat alternatives, were assessed. Meat alternatives containing potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea achieved the highest acceptance scores. Other protein sources, such as algae, insects, and different types of cultured meat, did not achieve high acceptance. Multiple regressions were used to investigate further the influence of consumer characteristics. For different types of protein sources, different consumer characteristics were identified as barriers, emphasizing the importance of distinguishing groups of consumers and types of protein sources. The study also showed that people's commitment to meat has no influence on their acceptance of alternative proteins; rather, negative attitudes to meat alternatives are the problem. Future efforts should therefore focus on optimizing the properties of meat alternatives, instead of demonizing the consumption of meat. One way to optimize the acceptance of meat alternatives is to use ingredients that consumers already have positive expectations toward, such as potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea.

1. Introduction

Meat eating has a long cultural history and tradition (Leroy & Praet, 2015) and is still considered the norm in Western societies. But meat production is responsible for severe environmental damages. It is the main driver for deforestation and associated with the loss of biodiversity (Machovina et al., 2015). Moreover, 15 % of human-made greenhouse gas emissions can be traced to livestock farming (Frezal et al., 2022). To feed the growing population on this planet sustainably, a transition to plant-based proteins is therefore desirable (Aiking & De Boer, 2020). Protein sources such as bean, lentil, and other legumes can be consumed as unprocessed ingredients in certain dishes. Other alternative protein sources can be found in food products with a long cultural tradition, such as tofu and seitan. In the last 20 years, the food industry has developed new meat alternatives using production techniques such as extrusion (Imran & Liyan, 2023). This second generation of meat alternatives imitates the look, taste, and texture of conventional meat and

aims to allow consumers to substitute meat more easily (Hoek et al., 2011). They can replace the meat component in recipes and build on existing eating habits. Even though a variety of such meat alternatives is widely available, and the detrimental effects of meat consumption is a frequently discussed topic in media and politics, the market share of meat alternatives is still very low. In Switzerland, meat alternatives accounted for less than 3 % of sales in the meat market in 2020 (Herrmann & Bolliger, 2021), and per capita meat consumption is not decreasing substantially (Federal Office for Agriculture, 2023). On the contrary, meat consumption is increasing in some regions of the world (Frezal et al., 2022). There are many reasons to believe that the meat market might not be as easily disrupted by meat alternatives as some scholar suggest (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2023).

Improving organoleptic properties and achieving price parity are necessary for the success of meat alternatives (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2023) and the food industry is experimenting with alternative protein sources as ingredients for meat alternatives. A wide range of promising

^{*} Corresponding author at: ETH Zurich, Department of Health Science and Technology (D-HEST), Consumer Behavior, CHN 18 J78, Universitätsstrasse 22, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland.

E-mail address: bruno.etter@hest.ethz.ch (B. Etter).

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plant-based proteins have been investigated (Good Food Institute, 2021). Additionally, microalgae and insects are used as protein sources in meat alternatives (Kurek et al., 2022). With cultured meat, yet another alternative protein source has been approved to enter the market in some countries, and more countries are expected to follow (Wiener-Bronner, 2023). However, most consumers already have certain expectations toward meat alternatives. Negative attitudes based on past experiences or other information and heuristics can prevent consumers from even trying new meat alternatives (Michel, Hartmann, et al., 2021). To increase consumer acceptance of meat alternatives, it is important to understand consumers' expectations and attitudes toward these different protein sources.

Because a systematic comparison of consumers' acceptance of a wide range of specific protein sources within the same study is still lacking (Onwezen et al., 2021), the present study compares 17 specific alternative protein sources and four conventional animal-based protein sources. The study aims to identify the most promising protein sources to use in meat alternatives from a consumer perspective and explores how consumer characteristics influence the acceptance of different protein sources.

1.1. Expectations toward different protein sources

A review by Onwezen et al. (2021) showed that consumer acceptance of insects and cultured meat has been investigated in various studies. However, the review only found a few studies comparing different protein sources within the same study. These studies compared cultured meat with plant-based meat alternatives (Bryant et al., 2019; Slade, 2018; Vural et al., 2023), pea-based with algae-based burgers (Michel, Knaapila, et al., 2021), insects with cultured meat and plant-based alternatives (Gómez-Luciano et al., 2019) and insects with cultured meat and algae (Grasso et al., 2019). Onwezen et al. (2021) found in their review that the acceptance level of alternative proteins is still low compared to conventional meat and that among alternative proteins, plant-based proteins are most accepted, while cultured meat and insects are least accepted. Most of these studies were conducted in Western European countries (Onwezen et al., 2021) and therefore reflect the view of western consumers. Expectations and acceptance of meat alternatives in general and certain alternative protein sources in specific depend on the food cultures and traditions consumers grow up with (Nguyen et al., 2022). In many Asian cultures algae (Mouritsen et al., 2018) and insects (Florenca et al., 2022) are for instance more accepted as food than in Europe.

The reviewed studies provide an incomplete picture even for western cultures because each study either focused on single protein sources or compared broad categories of protein sources (e.g., plant-based). We do not know, for instance, if treating all plant-based protein sources the same and using an overall category for them is justified from a consumer perspective. Also, it is unclear whether consumers have different expectations toward different types of cultured meat (e.g., beef, pork, or chicken). By including and comparing a wide range of specific protein sources, it is possible to gain a better understanding of how nuanced consumers' expectations and attitudes toward different protein sources are in the context of meat alternatives. Additionally, it enables the identification of specific promising protein sources, instead of only broad protein categories.

When it comes to measuring consumers' expectations it is important to keep in mind that consumers' perceptions and attitudes do not always match the objective attributes of food products (Hartmann et al., 2022). The natural-is-better heuristic, for instance, causes a halo that leads consumers to assume that natural products are automatically healthier and more environmentally friendly (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020a). Another example of biased consumer perceptions of food is the unhealthy = tasty intuition (Raghunathan et al., 2006), which describes the commonly found negative correlation between perceived healthiness and tastiness of food products. To better understand the

dimensionality of consumers' expectations, this study incorporates six measures of consumers' expectations, namely in regard to tastiness, healthiness, naturalness, and environmental friendliness, as well as their general affective evaluation and willingness to consume meat alternatives containing different protein sources. Tastiness and healthiness have been ranked among the most important motives for food choices across multiple European countries (Markovina et al., 2015). However, in the context of meat alternatives, environmental friendliness and perceived naturalness may have increased importance. Environmental friendliness is one of the major claimed benefits of these products compared to conventional meat products (Good Food Institute, 2023). The importance of consumers' naturalness perceptions was recently shown in the context of cultured meat. Across 10 countries, perceived naturalness was identified as a key mediator in predicting consumers' acceptance of cultured meat (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020b). Producing meat alternatives that imitate the properties of conventional meat often requires a high level of processing. The degree of processing has been shown to be an important factor influencing the perceived naturalness (Rozin, 2006) and perceived healthiness (Hässig et al., 2023) of a food product. In several studies, a high level of processing was identified as a main barrier for consumers to try meat alternatives (Collier et al., 2021; Varela et al., 2022). Producers therefore face a trade-off between using processing technology and additives to create meat-like products that consumers are familiar with and preserving a natural image of the product.

1.2. Influence of consumer characteristics

Investigating interindividual differences enables us to identify promising consumer groups for different protein sources. In addition, it gives insights into the factors driving or hindering the acceptance of different protein sources. While reviews of such drivers exist (Eckl et al., 2021; Onwezen et al., 2021), a direct comparison of drivers and inhibitors across different protein sources within the same study is lacking (Onwezen et al., 2021). The following personality characteristics are likely to play a particularly important role, since they are directly associated with relevant characteristics of protein sources: diet-related health consciousness, preference for naturalness, environmental identity, and food neophobia.

People with a high *diet-related health consciousness* have a higher intrinsic motivation to maintain good health and pay more attention to the health effects of the food they eat (Dutta-Bergman, 2005). Diet-related health consciousness has been found to be an influential factor for several eating behaviors and food choices, including the purchase of organic food (Schifferstein & Oude Ophuis, 1997), the use of nutritional information on food products (Visschers et al., 2013), the perceived risk of food hazards (Siegrist et al., 2022), and the consumption of meat alternatives (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019).

People also differ in how strong their *preference for naturalness* in food products is. A review by Román et al. (2017) showed that people with a stronger preference for naturalness prefer to eat traditional, ecological, healthy, and organic food and have more negative perceptions of novel food technologies.

Consumers' *environmental identity* is another factor likely to influence the perception of different alternative proteins. Studies have shown that consumers with stronger environmental concerns generally know more about the environmental impact of food products (Hartmann et al., 2021) and are more likely to choose a plant-based or cultured meat alternative (Slade, 2018). However, environmental values and concerns do not need to translate themselves directly into environmentally friendly behavior. The extent to which consumers self-identify as pro-environmental actors has been shown to have a more direct link to actual pro-environmental intentions and behaviors (Van der Werff et al., 2013). A recent study showed that triggering people's identity as sustainable actors can even be used as an intervention to increase the selection of meat-free meals in a free-choice experiment (Zinn et al.,

2023). Based on these results, we focus on consumers' environmental identity in the present study.

Food neophobia is a trait describing people's reluctance to eat new and unfamiliar food (Pliner & Hobden, 1992) and has repeatedly been found to be an important predictor for consumers' acceptance of alternative proteins (e.g., Hoek et al., 2011; Michel, Knaapila, et al., 2021).

Not only can the importance of different product characteristics differ from person to person but people can also have different overall attitudes toward meat and meat alternatives. *Meat commitment* (Piazza et al., 2015) and *meat attachment* (Graça et al., 2015) describe how important the consumption of meat is for consumers. Both measures have been found to be inhibitors of consumers' willingness to replace meat (Eckl et al., 2021; Onwezen et al., 2021). However, a high commitment to meat does not necessarily equal negative attitudes toward meat alternatives. We therefore use the *meat alternative rejection scale* (Wassmann et al., 2023) to also measure consumers' negative attitudes toward meat alternatives.

1.3. Aims of the study

By measuring consumers' expectations toward 17 alternative protein sources and four conventional animal-based protein sources on several rating dimensions, this study aims to find the most promising alternative protein sources for the use in meat alternatives. Additionally, the study explores the dimensionality of consumers' expectations by exploring the correlations between the different rating dimensions. Lastly, the study aims to compare the influence of relevant personality characteristics on consumers' acceptance of different types of alternative protein sources.

2. Methods

2.1. Study participants

The data for this study was collected in February 2023 in the German-speaking part of Switzerland using a professional panel provider for participant recruitment (Bilendi GmbH, Cologne). Participants were compensated for their participation according to the reimbursement policy of the panel provider. To be included in the study, participants had to be over 20 years old and identify as omnivores ("I eat all animal-based products") or flexitarians ("I eat meat only rarely"). A quota sampling method was used to guarantee an even distribution of men and women as well as of age groups (20–29, 30–39, 40–49, 50–59, 60+ years). Incomplete surveys, duplicates, and surveys that were filled out unusually fast (less than half of the median duration) were excluded from the sample. The final sample consisted of 916 completed surveys. Of these, 49% (n = 448) were completed by women and 51% (n = 465) were by men; less than 1% (n = 3) reported another gender or did not want to answer this question. The mean age of the sample was 47 years (SD = 16). Most participants (72%, n = 663), described themselves as omnivores, while 28% (n = 253) described themselves as flexitarians. Among the participants, 4% (n = 35) did not have a higher level of education than compulsory school, 44% (n = 401) had a vocational degree at the upper secondary level, 12% (n = 112) had a general education degree at the upper secondary level, 20% (n = 187) had higher vocational education, and 20% (n = 181) had a university degree.

2.2. Selection of protein sources

Based on current availability on the market and also a literature search, several potential alternative protein sources were preselected. The aim was to find a wide range of protein sources, that includes some established protein sources used in meat alternatives but also novel promising protein sources. After discussing this list of protein sources in several meetings with experts from the field of food science, 17 alternative protein sources were selected for this study. Twelve plant-based alternative protein sources were selected, namely soy, pea, chickpea,

lentil, rapeseed, sunflower seed, faba bean, wheat, potato, oat, quinoa, and rice. Soy, pea and wheat are the most often used protein sources in meat alternatives (Good Food Institute, 2021) and were chosen due to their strong position in the market. Chickpea and lentils were included as additional pulses consumers are familiar with and faba bean as a pulse that consumers are still rather unfamiliar with. Potato, oat, and rice are, like wheat, plants that are usually seen as carbohydrate compound in many meals but that can be used as a source of protein in meat alternatives. Quinoa is a pseudo cereal and was chosen due to its recent popularity as a superfood. Not only pulses and cereals can be used as protein sources but also oil seeds (Good Food Institute, 2021). To investigate how these protein sources fair compared with other plant-based proteins, we included rapeseed and sunflower seed. In addition, we included insects, algae, and three types of cultured meat (cultured beef, cultured pork, cultured chicken) as novel alternative protein sources. We also included four traditional animal-based protein sources, namely beef, pork, chicken, and egg, as references.

2.3. Structure of the survey

The survey was programmed using the online survey platform Qualtrics (Provo, UT). After a short unspecific description of the study and the general conditions, the participants gave their informed consent to take part in the study. The survey consisted of three main parts.

2.3.1. Sociodemographics

In the first part, we asked the participants to indicate their gender, age, highest education, and self-identified dietary style. They could choose between five dietary styles, which were described as follows: Omnivore (I eat all animal-based products), flexitarian (I eat meat only rarely), pescetarian (I do not eat meat, but fish and seafood), vegetarian (I eat neither meat nor fish), vegan (I do not eat any animal-based products at all).

2.3.2. Expectations toward different protein sources

The second and main part of the survey consisted of six rating dimensions, for which the participants had to rate their expectations toward meat alternatives (or meat respectively) made from each of the 21 protein sources on visual slider scales ranging from 0 to 100. At the start of this task, participants were given a short description of what a meat alternative is and it was emphasized that even if they have not tried a meat alternative containing one of the protein sources yet, their expectations are of interest. The six rating dimensions were general affect, taste, health, naturalness, environmental friendliness, and willingness to consume (WTC). The questions were phrased so that participants had to answer the questions relating to meat alternatives (in case of the alternative proteins) and relating to traditional meat (in case of the animal-based proteins). This way, a comparison between all protein types on the same scale was possible. The participants rated all proteins for one rating dimension before moving on to the next rating dimension. Table 1 shows the English translation of the task description and the rating questions.

2.3.3. Consumer characteristics

In the third part, several relevant consumer characteristics were measured using seven-point Likert scales (1 = *do not agree* at all, to 7 = *agree completely*, only the two endpoints were verbally labeled). The scales were presented in alternation with the questions measuring consumers' expectations toward the different protein sources described in Section 2.3.2 to make the questionnaire more enjoyable for the participants. It was ensured that the consumer characteristics that might have an influence on the responses of the rating questions were asked after the corresponding rating questions (e.g., preference for naturalness was measured after the naturalness ratings of the protein sources).

Health consciousness was measured with four items. The items were partially based on the health consciousness scale of Schifferstein

Table 1

Task description and rating dimensions for evaluation of the different protein sources.

Task description:		
Meat alternatives are designed to enable consumers to easily prepare meals without meat. They contain protein from alternative sources and imitate the properties of traditional meat products in terms of taste, texture, and appearance. At the same time, the nutritional value should be comparable to meat.		
We are interested in your opinion of meat alternatives made from different protein sources. Even if you have not yet consumed a product with one of the protein sources, we are interested in your assessment.		
Rating questions		
Dimension	Question	Endpoints of the scale
General affect	What is your general evaluation of the following proteins and protein sources?	0 = Very negative 100 = Very positive
Taste	How tasty do you expect meat substitutes (or meat respectively) made from the following proteins and protein sources to be?	0 = Not tasty at all 100 = Very tasty
Health	How healthy do you expect meat substitutes (or meat respectively) made from the following proteins and protein sources to be?	0 = Not healthy at all 100 = Very healthy
Naturalness	How natural do you expect meat substitutes (or meat respectively) made from the following proteins and protein sources to be?	0 = Not natural at all 100 = Very natural
Environment	How environmentally friendly do you expect meat substitutes (or meat respectively) made from the following proteins and protein sources to be?	0 = Not environmentally friendly at all 100 = Very environmentally friendly
WTC	How likely is it that you would consume a meat substitute (or meat respectively) made from the following proteins and protein sources?	0 = Not likely at all 100 = Very likely

and Oude Ophuis (1997) and yielded reliable results in previous studies (Dohle et al., 2014; Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019; Visschers et al., 2013). Example items are “I think it is important to eat healthily” and “I am prepared to leave a lot of food to eat as healthily as possible.” The scale reached a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.80$ in the present study.

Preference for naturalness. A recent review compared different scales used to measure preference for naturalness and concluded that the available scales correlate highly with each other (Michel & Siegrist, 2019). In accordance with the review’s suggestions, we employed a widely used scale, the six-item Natural Product Interest scale (Roininen et al., 1999). Example items are “I try to eat foods that do not contain additives” and “I do not eat processed foods, because I do not know what they contain.” The scale reached a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.72$ in the present study.

Environmental identity. To capture the self and social aspects of environmental identity, Brick et al. (2017) combined and modified items from a social identity scale (Smith et al., 2007) and an environmental self-identity scale (Van der Werff et al., 2013). We adapted the scale of Brick et al. (2017) for the purpose of the present study and measured environmental identity with five items. Example items are “I am a person who cares about the environment” and “I am a person who feels connected to other environmentally friendly people.” The five items reached a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.89$.

Food neophobia was measured with the 10-item German version (Siegrist et al., 2013) of the food neophobia scale (Pliner & Hobden, 1992). Example items are “I don’t trust new foods” and “If I don’t know what is in a food, I won’t try it.” The scale reached a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.85$ in the present study.

Meat commitment was measured with the seven-item meat commitment scale (Piazza et al., 2015). Example items are “I can’t imagine giving up meat” and “The best part of most meals is the meat

portion.” The scale reached a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.92$ in the present study.

Meat alternative rejection. Negative attitudes toward meat alternatives were measured with the recently developed 10-item meat alternative rejection scale, which has shown good psychometric properties (Wassmann et al., 2023). Example items are “Meat substitutes will never be able to adequately replace the taste of meat” and “Meat substitutes are only a temporary trend.” The scale reached a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.93$ in the present study.

2.4. Data analysis

IBM SPSS (version 28.0.1.1) and R (version 4.3.1) statistical software were used for data analysis. To investigate the dimensionality of consumers’ expectations toward different protein sources and to aggregate the data for further analyses, two types of principal component analyses (PCAs) were employed. The first series of PCAs investigated if the six rating dimensions (general affect, taste, healthiness, naturalness, environmental friendliness, and willingness to consume) can be aggregated for each of the 21 protein sources. The second PCA investigated how protein sources can be clustered based on participants’ acceptance ratings. Based on the results of the first PCA we then used ANOVA models and difference-adjusted confidence intervals (Baguley, 2012) to compare participants ratings between different protein sources but also between omnivores and flexitarians for each of the protein sources.

3. Results

3.1. Dimensionality of consumer expectations

To determine the dimensionality of consumers’ expectations toward meat alternatives containing different protein sources, a PCA of the six rating dimensions was conducted for each of the 21 protein sources. The PCAs all yielded similar results. A single principal component explained most of the variance in the rating dimensions (general affect, taste, healthiness, naturalness, environmental friendliness, and willingness to consume). The first principal component explained between 56 % and 70 % of the variance, depending on the protein source (see Table A1 in the Appendix for details). For further analysis, the rating dimensions were therefore combined into an overall acceptance score by taking the means of the six rating dimensions. For all protein sources, this acceptance scale reached good reliability, with a Cronbach’s Alpha of $\alpha = 0.83$ or higher.

3.2. Comparison of proteins and dietary styles

A repeated measures ANOVA using the Greenhouse–Geisser correction showed that the acceptance scores of the 21 protein sources differed significantly from each other ($F(5.22, 4779.62) = 449.06, p < 0.001$). Fig. 1 uses confidence intervals to show in detail between which protein sources significant differences can be found. Because the proteins were rated in a within-subject design, we used adjusted Cousineau–Morey confidence intervals (Baguley, 2012; Cousineau, 2005; Morey, 2008). These confidence intervals adjust not only for the higher power in repeated measures designs but also for the increased uncertainty of comparing means with each other instead of with a prespecified value. This way, non-overlapping confidence intervals correspond with a significant difference between the means in a repeated measures ANOVA (Baguley, 2012). Using such confidence intervals instead of p -values allows for the efficient comparison of multiple means (Goldstein & Healy, 1995). The three cultured meat types achieved the lowest acceptance of all protein sources. Insects also had low acceptance scores, but these were significantly higher than those of the cultured meat types. Algae and the plant-based proteins all had acceptance scores above the neutral middle of the scale (50). Potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea were the plant-based protein sources with the highest acceptance scores and

Fig. 1. Within-subject comparison of acceptance scores of the protein sources.

Note: The error bars are adjusted Cousineau–Morey 99% confidence intervals. Non-overlapping confidence intervals correspond to a significant difference between means at a 0.01 alpha level.

were perceived as positively as chicken and beef. Soy and rapeseed had the lowest acceptance of all plant-based proteins. Among the conventional animal-based proteins, egg achieved the highest acceptance scores, while pork had significantly lower acceptance than chicken, beef, and egg.

A MANOVA analysis showed that omnivores and flexitarians differed in their acceptance of the different protein sources ($F(21, 894) = 8.35$,

$p < 0.001$). Fig. 2 uses confidence intervals to show in detail for which protein sources significant differences between omnivores and flexitarians could be found. We used Tryon-adjusted confidence intervals to visualize significant differences between the dietary styles (Tryon, 2001). These confidence intervals adjust for the increased uncertainty of comparing means with each other in a between-subject design (Cousineau et al., 2021; Tryon, 2001). For all plant-based protein sources,

Fig. 2. Between-subject comparison of acceptance scores of omnivores and flexitarians Note: The error bars are Tryon-adjusted 99% confidence intervals. Non-overlapping confidence intervals correspond to a significant difference between group means at a 0.01 alpha level.

omnivorous participants showed a lower acceptance score than flexitarian participants. The differences were, however, smaller for the three typical starch sources of potato, rice, and wheat. No significant differences could be found for cultured meat and insects. While the three traditional meat types beef, pork, and chicken were clearly less accepted by flexitarians, no significant difference could be found for egg. The most accepted alternative protein sources for omnivores and flexitarians were potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea.

3.3. Drivers of and barriers to the acceptance of different alternative protein sources

Using the acceptance scores, we conducted a further PCA, this time not on the rating dimensions but on the protein sources. The aim was to group the protein sources in a smaller number of clusters in order to reduce the number of regression analyses needed for examining the impact of consumer characteristics on the perception of alternative proteins. Based on a scree plot and the ease of interpretation, a solution with four components was best suited to group the protein sources. The four principal components explained 84 % of the variance and were therefore sufficient to describe consumers' acceptance patterns of different protein sources. The principal components were as follows: plant-based, conventional animal-based, cultured meat, and insects. The standardized loadings of the protein sources on the four components can be found in Table 2. The only protein source with high cross-loadings was algae, which loaded almost as high on the fourth component (insects) as it did on the first component (plant-based). Because algae could not be assigned clearly to one of the two components, it is hereinafter analyzed separately. For the plant-based protein sources, the mean of the acceptance score of all 12 protein sources was calculated for each participant. This plant-based acceptance scale reached a Cronbach's Alpha of $\alpha = 0.98$. The acceptance of the three cultured meat types was also aggregated by taking the mean. This cultured meat acceptance scale reached a Cronbach's Alpha of $\alpha = 0.98$. The four conventional animal-based protein sources were aggregated as well, and the corresponding scale reached a Cronbach's Alpha of $\alpha = 0.91$.

Table 3 shows how the acceptance scores of the five groups of protein

Table 2
Varimax rotated PCA of the acceptance scores of the protein sources (four components).

Protein	Standardized loadings			
	PC1: Plant-based	PC2: Conventional animal-based	PC3: Cultured meat	PC4: Insects
Soy	0.78	0.07	0.24	0.26
Pea	0.91	0.13	0.08	0.16
Chickpea	0.89	0.08	0.08	0.25
Lentil	0.89	0.08	0.08	0.24
Rapeseed	0.84	0.12	0.20	0.20
Sunflower	0.88	0.15	0.16	0.12
Faba	0.82	0.10	0.17	0.31
Wheat	0.87	0.20	0.20	-0.01
Potato	0.88	0.24	0.11	-0.11
Oat	0.89	0.11	0.16	0.12
Quinoa	0.80	0.03	0.11	0.37
Rice	0.88	0.22	0.17	-0.07
Algae ¹	0.62	0.06	0.21	0.61
Insects	0.38	0.13	0.36	0.71
Cult. Beef	0.20	0.12	0.95	0.11
Cult. Pork	0.20	0.12	0.93	0.14
Cult. Chicken	0.20	0.11	0.94	0.11
Beef	0.07	0.93	0.08	0.01
Pork	0.05	0.82	0.17	0.02
Chicken	0.15	0.92	0.10	0.07
Egg	0.35	0.78	0.00	0.08
Proportion variance	0.46	0.16	0.15	0.07

Note. ¹Algae cannot be clearly assigned to one of the principal components due to high cross-loadings; loadings > 0.50 appear in bold font.

sources correlate with each other and also with age, gender, and different consumer characteristics. To better understand how these consumer characteristics influence the acceptance of the different protein sources, five separate multiple regression analyses were conducted using the aggregated acceptance scores of the protein groups as outcomes and the consumer characteristics as predictors. Even though some of the predictors showed medium to high intercorrelations (see Table 3), the tolerance and the variance inflation factor (VIF) did not reach concerning levels for any of the predictors (lowest tolerance = .53, highest VIF = 1.90). Table 4 shows the results of the five regression analyses. The predictors together explain between 24 % and 26 % of the variance in participants' acceptance of plant-based proteins, algae, and insects. For cultured meat and conventional animal-based proteins, 13 % and 11 %, respectively, of the variance could be explained.

The only predictor having a significant effect on all types of alternative proteins was *meat alternative rejection*. The higher participants' meat alternative rejection, the lower was their acceptance of plant-based proteins, algae, insects, and cultured meat. In contrast, *meat commitment* only significantly predicted the acceptance of conventional animal-based proteins but none of the alternative proteins.

Food neophobia was significantly associated with a lower acceptance of plant-based proteins, algae, and insects. The opposite pattern could be observed for environmental identity. *Environmental identity* had a positive effect on the acceptance of plant-based proteins, algae, and insects. Both food neophobia and environmental identity did not influence the acceptance of cultured meat or conventional animal-based proteins.

Health consciousness and *preference for naturalness* also showed opposite effects on some of the protein sources. While health consciousness had a significantly positive impact on the acceptance of plant-based proteins, insects, and cultured meat, preference for naturalness had a significant negative impact on the acceptance of insects and cultured meat.

Being a woman and *older age* were both significantly associated with a lower acceptance of algae, insects, and cultured meat. Being a woman additionally had a significant negative effect on the acceptance of conventional animal-based proteins. The acceptance of plant-based proteins was, however, not significantly affected by gender or age.

4. Discussion

The present study examined consumers' attitudes to a variety of protein sources for use in meat alternatives. Across the different conventional and alternative proteins, different expectation dimensions, such as tastiness, healthiness, naturalness, and environmental friendliness, were found to be highly intercorrelated. PCAs showed that consumers' expectations can be described with a one-dimensional acceptance score. Similarly, Hartmann et al. (2022) found healthiness, environmental friendliness, and naturalness evaluations of meat alternatives to be intercorrelated and often not to match the objective properties of the products. Heuristic processing of food products might explain this pattern. For example, the natural-is-better and the affect heuristic can strongly influence consumers' evaluation of new food products (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020a). This has implications not only for the marketing of meat alternatives but also for measuring consumers' expectations in future research. A negative attitude to one aspect of an ingredient can potentially taint consumers' expectations toward the whole product.

The analysis of an aggregated acceptance score showed that protein sources varied greatly in their consumer acceptance. For the use in meat alternatives egg was the most accepted protein source overall, whereas potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea were the most promising alternative protein sources. Other plant-based protein sources, such as soy and rapeseed, and also algae reached lower acceptance. The lowest acceptance was found for insects and all types of cultured meat. Consumers are very conservative when it comes to food and hard to convince to try new food products (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020a). It is important to use

Table 3
Pearson correlations between the predictors and outcome variables in the analyses (N = 913).

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1 Age												
2 Women	-.02											
3 Food neophobia	.14**	-.01										
4 Health consciousness	.04	-.02	-.17**									
5 Preference for naturalness	.12**	.08	-.03	.47**								
6 Environmental identity	.11**	.02	-.13**	.47**	.42**							
7 Meat commitment	.01	-.23**	.24**	-.19**	-.28**	-.26**						
8 Meat alternative rejection	.14**	-.09*	.35**	-.13**	-.12**	-.19**	.63**					
9 Acceptance plant-based	-.12**	.03	-.36**	.23**	.08	.27**	-.28**	-.40**				
10 Acceptance algae	-.14**	-.06	-.39**	.21**	.11**	.22**	-.23**	-.35**	.74**			
11 Acceptance insects	-.21**	-.12**	-.37**	.15**	-.04	.14**	-.14**	-.31**	.57**	.68**		
12 Acceptance cultured meat	-.17**	-.12**	-.15**	.06	-.14**	.05	-.06	-.23**	.40**	.41**	.50**	
13 Acceptance animal-based	-.08	-.16**	-.03	.02	-.09*	-.02	.29**	.14**	.33**	.22**	.25**	.26**

Note. * p < 0.01, ** p < 0.001; acceptance plant-based = mean of the acceptance score of soy, pea, chickpea, lentil, rapeseed, sunflower, faba bean, wheat, potato, oat, quinoa, and rice; acceptance algae = acceptance score of algae; acceptance insects = acceptance score of insects; acceptance cultured meat = mean of the acceptance score of cultured beef, cultured pork, and cultured chicken; acceptance animal-based = mean of the acceptance score of beef, pork, chicken, and egg. Participants who did not identify as men or women (n = 3) were excluded from the analysis due to the small sample size of this group.

protein sources toward which consumers already have positive expectations to expand the customer base of meat alternatives. The overall pattern that plant-based protein sources are more accepted than insects and cultured meat (Onwezen et al., 2021) was confirmed in our study. Among the plant-based protein sources, potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea were most promising. These protein sources were also found to be among the most popular ingredients in plant-based food in earlier studies (Brechtold et al., 2021). One can think of several reasons why consumers have more positive expectations toward these plant-based ingredients compared to others. One explanation could be that consumers are already more familiar with these ingredients. Past research showed that because familiarity goes along with reduced uncertainty and suspicion, familiar food is normally more accepted than unfamiliar food (Aldridge et al., 2009; Tuorila & Hartmann, 2020). Research has also shown that the acceptance of novel food can be improved by increasing the familiarity people associate with the food, for instance by making it more available and visible (Aldridge et al., 2009). Using familiar ingredients is one way to increase the familiarity consumers associate with a meat alternative. Potatoes, in particular, are very important in Swiss food culture. Many traditional recipes are potato based (e.g. rösti and raclette), and Swiss consumers eat on average 49 kg of potatoes per year (Agristat, 2022). This might explain why meat alternatives containing potatoes but also lentils or peas seem to have an advantage over meat alternatives containing less familiar ingredients, such as faba bean or quinoa.

Low familiarity is also likely to be the reason why algae received low acceptance scores. Food neophobia turned out to be the strongest predictor for the acceptance of algae in the regression analysis, emphasizing the importance of lacking familiarity. While algae is a common ingredient in Asian cuisine, it is rather unknown in Western diets (Lafarga et al., 2021). Not only has Switzerland no tradition of algae as food but fish and seafood are also not often consumed, especially in the German-speaking part of the country (Agristat, 2022; Kopf-Bolan & Walther, 2021). Meat alternatives containing algae are likely to be better accepted in Asia, where algae are traditionally used as food, and consumers in European countries with higher fish and seafood consumption might also have more positive associations with an aquatic ingredient.

Even though soy is a familiar protein source for many people, it achieved lower acceptance in our study than most other plant-based protein sources. This could be due to negative taste experiences with first-generation meat alternatives, which often contained soy (e.g., tofu). Other possible explanations are negative associations with genetically modified (GMO) soy and erroneous beliefs about the relationship between soy production and deforestation. European consumers show in general low acceptance of GMO crops (Gaskell et al., 2011) and the association of soy with gene technology in media coverage might lead to

negative associations with soy in general. Additionally, research by Siegrist and Hartmann (2019) showed that consumers tend to underestimate the sustainability of soy-based food products. The authors suspected that consumers may not effectively distinguish between soy used for animal feed and soy for human consumption within the context of deforestation concerns (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2019).

The strongest predictor for the acceptance of insects in the present study was food neophobia, indicating that many consumers do not perceive insects as part of a conventional diet. Another barrier for consumers' acceptance identified in the literature is disgust reactions (Ruby et al., 2015). Changing the association of insects with disgust is a big challenge (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2017) and makes it difficult to familiarize consumers with insects as food.

In contrast to earlier studies (Onwezen et al., 2021), we found the acceptance of cultured meat to be even lower than the acceptance of insects. The regression analysis showed that participants' food neophobia did not explain the low acceptance of cultured meat, but their preference for naturalness did. For cultured meat, a lack of familiarity may therefore not be the most pressing problem; rather, it is the low perceived naturalness. This aligns with the results of Siegrist et al. (2018), who found that consumers' low naturalness perception mediated their low willingness to consume cultured meat. For conventional meat, participants perceived chicken and beef as much more acceptable than pork. For cultured meat, this pattern was not as clear, as all types of cultured meat received very low acceptance scores. This might be explained by strong negative associations with the production method of cultured meat that overshadow consumers' attitudes toward different types of meat. So far, studies have not systematically investigated how consumers perceive different types of cultured meat. However, our results align with those of Garcez de Oliveira Padilha et al. (2022), who did not find big differences between consumers' perceptions of cultured beef and cultured chicken. The perception of naturalness can be improved by adjusting the external characteristics of cultured meat products, for instance by using names and labels that do not emphasize the production method (Bryant & Dillard, 2019; Bryant & Barnett, 2019). If this is enough for cultured meat to be successful on the market is, however, not guaranteed.

A promising and feasible way to attract new consumers is to use already accepted alternative protein sources, such as potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea. Across all the protein sources investigated, egg achieved the highest acceptance score. Because egg is a conventional animal-based product, it is rarely discussed as an alternative to meat in the literature. In some meat alternatives, egg white is used to optimize the texture of the product (Kumar et al., 2017). The current study shows that egg is perceived as extremely positive by omnivores and flexitarians and that meat alternatives featuring egg as a protein source are likely to

Table 4
Regression models predicting the acceptance of five groups of protein sources using consumer characteristics (N = 913).

Outcome: Mean acceptance score of different protein groups															
Predictor	Plant-based $F(8, 904) = 41.04, p < 0.001, \text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.26$			Algae $F(8, 904) = 36.44, p < 0.001, \text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.24$			Insects $F(8, 904) = 36.10, p < 0.001, \text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.24$			Cultured meat $F(8, 904) = 17.59, p < 0.001, \text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.13$			Conventional meats & egg $F(8, 904) = 15.00, p < 0.001, \text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.11$		
	B	99 % CI	β	B	99 % CI	β	B	99 % CI	β	B	99 % CI	β	B	99 % CI	β
Women	0.09	[-2.94; 3.12]	.00	-4.11	[-7.78; -0.44]	-.09*	-6.17	[-10.02; -2.32]	-.12**	-5.20	[-9.25; -1.26]	-.11**	-3.45	[-6.57; -0.34]	-.09*
Age	-0.08	[-0.18; 0.02]	-.06	-0.14	[-0.26; -0.02]	-.09*	-0.23	[-0.35; -0.10]	-.14**	-0.19	[-0.31; -0.06]	-.12**	-0.09	[-0.19; 0.01]	-.08
Food neophobia	-3.85	[-5.27; -2.42]	-.22**	-5.95	[-7.67; -4.22]	-.28**	-5.75	[-7.56; -3.94]	-.26**	-0.80	[-2.65; 1.06]	-.04	-1.31	[-2.78; 0.15]	-.08
Health consciousness	2.07	[0.54; 3.59]	.12**	1.54	[-0.31; 3.39]	.08	2.34	[0.40; 4.28]	.11*	2.22	[0.23; 4.21]	.11*	0.93	[-0.64; 2.50]	.06
Pref. for naturalness	-1.54	[-3.20; 0.11]	-.08	0.32	[-1.68; 2.32]	.01	-2.97	[-5.07; -0.87]	-.13**	-4.82	[-6.97; -2.67]	-.22**	-0.70	[-2.39; 1.00]	-.04
Environmental identity	2.87	[1.38; 4.37]	.17**	2.36	[0.56; 4.17]	.12**	2.08	[0.18; 3.98]	.10*	1.45	[-0.50; 3.39]	.07	0.81	[-0.72; 2.35]	.05
Meat commitment	-0.06	[-1.35; 1.23]	-.00	0.09	[-1.46; 1.65]	.01	0.96	[-0.68; 2.59]	.06	0.96	[-0.71; 2.64]	.06	3.73	[2.40; 5.05]	.31**
Meat alternative rejection	-3.85	[-5.23; -2.47]	-.28**	-3.53	[-5.20; -1.85]	-.21**	-4.08	[-5.84; -2.32]	-.24**	-4.15	[-5.95; -2.35]	-.25**	-0.17	[-1.59; 1.25]	-.01

Note. * $p < .01$, ** $p < .001$; acceptance plant-based = mean of the acceptance score of soy, pea, chickpea, lentil, rapeseed, sunflower, faba bean, wheat, potato, oat, quinoa, and rice; acceptance algae = acceptance score of algae; acceptance insects = acceptance score of insects; acceptance cultured meat = mean of the acceptance score of cultured beef, cultured pork, and cultured chicken; acceptance animal-based = mean of the acceptance score of beef, pork, chicken, and egg. Participants who did not identify as men or women ($n = 3$) were excluded from the analysis due to the small sample size of this group.

receive high acceptance rates among a large consumer group. Life-cycle assessments have shown that eggs are among the animal-based products with the lowest environmental impact and, in some respects, even comparable with plant-based products (Clark et al., 2022; Poore & Nemecek, 2019). Further research is, however, required to better understand the sustainability potential of egg as a meat alternative.

There is no one size fits all solution, and no single product can appeal to all consumers. It is therefore important to offer different types of meat alternatives in terms of their main ingredients and degree of meat similarity. The regression analyses showed that people's commitment to meat is not the main barrier for the acceptance of meat alternatives, it is rather the negative attitudes they have toward meat alternatives. To increase acceptance of meat alternatives overall, it is therefore not advisable to demonize the consumption of meat but to instead work on improving consumers' attitudes toward meat alternatives. The sensory appeal of food products is among the most important factors influencing food choices (Markovina et al., 2015), and improving the organoleptic properties of meat alternatives is therefore a necessary requirement to change consumers' attitudes. Using ingredients that consumers are familiar with and have positive expectations toward, such as potato, lentil, pea, chickpea, and egg, can further improve consumers' attitudes and motivate consumers to try new meat alternatives.

4.1. Limitations

By comparing a wide range of specific protein sources along different rating dimensions, this study was able to capture consumers' expectation with a high level of detail. However, our approach also comes with some limitations. Past research shows that consumers' expectations of alternative protein sources can depend on how tangible they are presented as food products (Embling et al., 2022). In a study by Embling et al. (2022) consumers had more positive taste and familiarity expectations, but less positive healthiness and naturalness expectations towards specific seaweed based food products compared to a generic description of seaweed as ingredient. We emphasized in the task description that the participants should think of meat alternatives containing the respective protein sources when stating their expectations. However, we did not define what the specific characteristics of the meat alternatives in question were. Instead, we gave very limited information to not restrict consumers' thinking and expectations toward the protein sources. It is therefore not guaranteed that the patterns we found in this study stay true for all types of meat alternatives. Additionally, it could be that some protein sources are more difficult for consumers to picture as part of a meat alternative product than others. This could have influenced their ratings in this study and could also be a potential barrier of acceptance in real-life shopping situations.

The consumer characteristics investigated in the present study give valuable insights, but they should not be seen as an exhaustive list of influential factors. Other consumer characteristics, such as disgust sensitivity (Hartmann & Siegrist, 2020), are also important for the acceptance of certain alternative protein sources, but were not measured.

Additionally, our study was only conducted in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. Because consumers' experiences of and familiarity with certain protein sources are likely to differ depending on cultural regions, it is possible that certain protein sources are judged differently in other countries. Future studies should therefore compare different regions and different types of products.

4.2. Conclusion

Familiar and plant-based protein sources have an advantage over other ingredients in meat alternatives when it comes to consumer acceptance. This study identified potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea as the most promising protein sources for the use in meat alternatives. In particular, health-conscious consumers with a strong environmental identity tend to see plant-based protein sources in a positive light. Algae achieved rather low acceptance in this study. However, it might be a more promising ingredient in other food cultures where consumers are more familiar with algae and other aquatic ingredients. The results of the present study indicate that it will be difficult to convince consumers of insects and cultured meat as meat alternatives. In particular, people's preference for naturalness is a main barrier for all types of cultured meat, and this must be considered for the marketing of such products. The study also showed that consumers' acceptance of meat alternatives does not depend so much on their meat commitment but rather on negative attitudes toward meat alternatives. For this reason, future efforts should focus on improving the product characteristics of meat alternatives instead of demonizing the consumption of meat. By considering consumers' expectations and using protein sources with high acceptance, such as potato, lentil, chickpea, and pea, producers of meat alternatives are more likely to attract new consumers.

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Ethical statement

Participants gave informed consent via the statement "Yes, I would like to participate in this survey and confirm that I have read the information. The data provided in this survey will be evaluated anonymously and is for purely scientific purposes" where an affirmative reply was required to enter the survey. They were able to withdraw from the survey at any time without giving a reason. The study was approved by the ETH Zurich Ethics Commission on the 6th of February 2023 (proposal No EK 2023-N-13).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Bruno Etter: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Fabienne Michel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Michael Siegrist:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare financial support was provided by Horizon Europe.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix

Table A1

Results of the PCAs of the six rating dimensions for the 21 protein sources.

Protein	Cronbach's Alpha	Eigenvalue of first component	Variance explained (%)	Standardized loadings on first component					
				General affect	Taste	Health	Naturalness	Environment	wtc
Soy	0.88	3.77	63	0.78	0.80	0.86	0.80	0.73	0.77
Pea	0.89	3.87	65	0.73	0.81	0.87	0.82	0.78	0.80
Chickpea	0.89	3.93	65	0.76	0.81	0.89	0.82	0.77	0.80
Lentil	0.89	3.94	66	0.75	0.81	0.88	0.83	0.79	0.80
Rapeseed	0.88	3.73	62	0.72	0.80	0.87	0.82	0.74	0.78
Sunflower	0.88	3.78	63	0.71	0.80	0.87	0.80	0.79	0.79
Faba	0.89	3.91	65	0.77	0.83	0.86	0.82	0.76	0.80
Wheat	0.87	3.69	62	0.67	0.79	0.87	0.82	0.76	0.78
Potato	0.87	3.68	61	0.60	0.81	0.85	0.85	0.79	0.77
Oat	0.88	3.79	63	0.73	0.81	0.87	0.82	0.78	0.80
Quinoa	0.90	4.03	67	0.80	0.83	0.88	0.82	0.76	0.82
Rice	0.88	3.76	63	0.69	0.80	0.87	0.82	0.79	0.76
Algae	0.88	3.72	62	0.78	0.79	0.86	0.79	0.72	0.78
Insect	0.88	3.78	63	0.78	0.76	0.87	0.81	0.80	0.73
Cultured beef	0.91	4.16	69	0.80	0.86	0.88	0.84	0.78	0.82
Cultured pork	0.90	4.03	67	0.80	0.85	0.86	0.83	0.77	0.80
Cultured chicken	0.92	4.23	70	0.83	0.87	0.88	0.84	0.78	0.83
Beef	0.83	3.33	56	0.69	0.78	0.83	0.80	0.62	0.74
Pork	0.87	3.62	60	0.73	0.84	0.83	0.76	0.71	0.78
Chicken	0.84	3.41	57	0.67	0.78	0.84	0.81	0.65	0.74
Egg	0.84	3.42	57	0.65	0.77	0.85	0.82	0.71	0.72

Note. wtc = willingness to consume.

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